

Development of an Interactive Sound Generation System Based on Quantum Game Theory

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Abstract. We present a web-based interactive music system that generates sound through the framework of two-player quantum game theory. Two users connect via a internet browser interface, select quantum strategies, and trigger notes by pressing piano keys. Each input initiates a two-qubit circuit whose measurement probabilistically collapses into one of four outcomes, each linked to a payoff pair inspired by the Prisoner's Dilemma. These sampled payoffs determine pitch shifts relative to a neutral baseline, producing distinct sounds for each player. The system provides real-time visual and auditory feedback, allowing participants to perceive how their own strategies intertwine with those of their opponent through quantum interference and measurement. Beyond applications in music and education, the framework also models improvisatory interplay-akin to jazz performance-where each player's decision reshapes the shared horizon of possible outcomes. This platform opens new avenues for exploring quantum games, human-computer interaction, and entangled decision-making through sound.

1 Introduction

Quantum computing offers multiple perspectives for musical applications, including sound generation itself, static aspects such as harmony and chord structure, and the temporal flow of music as a progression over time. It is conceivable that quantum logic can be reflected not only in each of these elements but also in the very connections among them. Needless to say, each aspect should be examined both carefully and ambitiously, in alignment with the progress of quantum information science and the development of quantum computers, always with a focus on identifying what advantages or unique features arise specifically from the use of quantum technologies.

In recent years, a number of pioneering studies have explored the intersection between quantum computing and musical expression. Miranda and Basak [1] have laid the groundwork by proposing foundational concepts and initial experimental frameworks in quantum computer music. Oshiro [2] has implemented beat generation using quantum algorithms through the application "QuiKo", illustrating the practical potential of quantum logic in rhythmic structures. Meanwhile, Itaborai and Miranda [3] investigated how mechanical wave-based representations of sound could be reformulated within the formalism of quantum circuits.

Other research has explored algorithmic applications: Mistry and Ortega [4] applied quantum Fourier

transforms to frequency detection tasks, suggesting novel perspectives on pitch recognition and spectral analysis. Finally, Miranda et al. [5] introduced a fascinating approach to musical intelligence using quantum natural language processing (QNLP), opening a dialogue between symbolic musical reasoning and quantum computational semantics. Applications of quantum computing to music have also been explored from different perspectives, including the use of various quantum algorithms, quantum live coding approaches, and the initial concept of applying quantum game theory [6]. More recently, quantum-inspired models of improvisation in networked musical contexts have been proposed [7].

These studies collectively suggest that quantum computation can offer new tools not only for musical generation, but also for the deeper structural and cognitive aspects of music. While many of these works focus on algorithmic sound generation, symbolic representation, or conceptual frameworks, there remains a need for systems that enable embodied, real-time interaction between multiple users in a quantum-informed musical setting.

We present the development of a web-based interactive sound generation system driven by quantum game theory. The system allows two users to participate remotely via a browser interface, select quantum strategies, and trigger sound playback through piano key input. When a key is pressed by either user, the server constructs and executes a quantum circuit reflecting the current strategic parameters of both players. The measurement outcome of the circuit determines individual payoffs according to a predefined quantum game payoff table, inspired by the Prisoner's Dilemma.

2 Quantum Game Theory for Interactive Music Performance

2.1 Overview of Quantum Game Theory

Game theory is a branch of decision theory that provides a mathematical framework for analyzing strategic interactions among rational agents. It addresses situations in which the outcome for each participant depends not only on their own choices but also on the actions of others. As such, game theory is widely applied in fields such as economics, political science, computer science, and evolutionary biology. Its formal foundation was laid by John von Neumann and Oscar Morgenstern in their seminal book, *The Theory of Games and Economic Behavior* (1944) [8].

The expected payoffs for Alice and Bob are then computed as weighted sums over the measurement probabilities in the computational basis:

$$\bar{\pi}_A = 3 |\langle 00 | \Psi_f \rangle|^2 + 0 |\langle 01 | \Psi_f \rangle|^2 + 5 |\langle 10 | \Psi_f \rangle|^2 + 1 |\langle 11 | \Psi_f \rangle|^2, \quad (5)$$

$$\bar{\pi}_B = 3 |\langle 00 | \Psi_f \rangle|^2 + 5 |\langle 01 | \Psi_f \rangle|^2 + 0 |\langle 10 | \Psi_f \rangle|^2 + 1 |\langle 11 | \Psi_f \rangle|^2. \quad (6)$$

This formulation applies to any combination of strategies (s_A, s_B) . For example, when both players choose to defect, i.e., $U_A = \sigma_x$ and $U_B = \sigma_x$, the final state becomes

$$|\Psi_f(\sigma_x, \sigma_x)\rangle = |11\rangle, \quad (7)$$

resulting in payoffs $\bar{\pi}_A = \bar{\pi}_B = 1$, consistent with the classical payoff table (see Fig. 1(a)).

In the quantum version of the Prisoner's Dilemma, the strategy operators U_A and U_B are generalized to unitary operation:

$$U(\theta, \varphi) = U_3(\theta, \varphi, \pi) = \begin{pmatrix} \cos \frac{\theta}{2} & \sin \frac{\theta}{2} \\ e^{i\varphi} \sin \frac{\theta}{2} & -e^{i\varphi} \cos \frac{\theta}{2} \end{pmatrix}, \quad (8)$$

which allows for a continuum of quantum strategies (θ, ϕ) beyond the classical discrete choices. In particular, $U(0, \pi) = I$ corresponds to classical cooperation (C), while $U(\pi, 0) = \sigma_x$ corresponds to classical defection (D).

Other angles represent genuinely quantum strategies. For example, $U(\pi/2, 0) = H$ corresponds to the Hadamard gate, and $U(0, 0) = \sigma_z$ corresponds to the Z gate. These quantum strategies can lead to non-classical outcomes. For instance, if Alice selects $U_A = \sigma_z$ and Bob selects $U_B = \sigma_x$, the final state becomes $|\Psi_f\rangle = |10\rangle$, meaning that Alice's effective move becomes D and Bob's becomes C—a reversal of Bob's original intent. Conversely, if Alice chooses σ_x and Bob chooses σ_z , then $|\Psi_f\rangle = |01\rangle$, which implies that Alice's move is effectively C and Bob's is D.

These examples demonstrate that quantum strategies can induce *context-dependent outcomes* due to interference and entanglement, potentially altering a player's effective move depending on the opponent's strategy. This is a core difference from classical game theory, where strategy choices are independent and deterministic in outcome. For further details on quantum game theoretical analysis, we refer the reader to [11]. In the next section, we explore how this framework can be integrated into an interactive system for real-time musical expression.

In the previous study [6], a two-player quantum game model was applied to sequential musical note generation. In that approach, each note was associated with a predefined measurement axis on the circle of fifths, and the measurement results of the players' qubits were interpreted along those axes. Specifically, the computational basis states $|0\rangle$ and $|1\rangle$ of a qubit were mapped to two pitches separated by π radians on the circle, such as C and

F \sharp , or G and D \flat . These measurement axes were manually assigned in advance for each note timing, effectively integrating compositional structure into the quantum measurement process.

In contrast, the present work proposes an alternative methodology in which the keystroke on a virtual piano interface is treated as a meta-strategy. The input note, rather than being a target of measurement, provides contextual information that influences the interpretation of the quantum game outcome. This dynamic strategy is implemented through a browser-based interactive system, where each key press triggers quantum circuit execution, payoff evaluation, and sound playback. The approach allows for real-time participation by multiple users and enables an intuitive, sound-based exploration of quantum strategic interaction.

2.2 Quantum Interference and Mixed Outcomes

In the quantum formulation of the Prisoner's Dilemma, each player chooses a unitary strategy operator, U_A and U_B , acting locally on their respective qubits. The system is initially prepared in an entangled state through the operator J , and the final quantum state $|\psi_f\rangle$ after the strategies have been applied is given by Eq. (4). This state $|\psi_f\rangle$ is a pure state that encodes all potential outcomes as a coherent superposition. Unlike the classical case, where strategies only determine deterministic outcomes, in the quantum case the amplitudes of $|\psi_f\rangle$ depend jointly on both players' strategies, giving rise to *quantum interference between strategies*.

To illustrate this effect, the final state can be expanded as

$$|\psi_f\rangle = c_{00}|00\rangle + c_{01}|01\rangle + c_{10}|10\rangle + c_{11}|11\rangle, \quad (9)$$

with complex amplitudes c_{ij} determined by (U_A, U_B) . The measurement probabilities in the computational basis are then

$$P_{ij} = |\langle ij | \psi_f \rangle|^2 = |c_{ij}|^2. \quad (10)$$

In contrast to classical mixed strategies, these probabilities cannot in general be written as independent products of the players' choices; instead, they include interference terms such as $\text{Re}(c_{00}^* c_{01})$ or $\text{Im}(c_{10}^* c_{11})$, reflecting contextual and non-local correlations. This interference means that the effective action of one player may be altered by the other's choice, even without direct communication.

The classical payoffs are recovered only after measurement, which yields a definite outcome from $\{|00\rangle, |01\rangle, |10\rangle, |11\rangle\}$ with probabilities $\{P_{00}, P_{01}, P_{10}, P_{11}\}$. This measurement process can be described as a transition from the pure state $|\psi_f\rangle$ to a classical probability distribution over outcomes.

The above discussion can be reformulated more systematically by introducing the density matrix formalism. The measurement-induced mixed state is given by

$$\rho = \sum_{ij} P_{ij} |ij\rangle \langle ij|, \quad (11)$$

where the index (i, j) plays the role of a composite label for the classical outcomes. In this formulation, the classical payoff matrix for Alice/Bob is elevated to the quantum payoff operator

$$\hat{\Pi}_{A/B} = \sum_{ij} \Pi_{A/B}(ij) |ij\rangle\langle ij|, \quad (12)$$

and the expected payoff is compactly expressed as

$$\bar{\pi}_{A/B} = \text{Tr}(\rho \hat{\Pi}_{A/B}) = \sum_{ij} P_{ij} \Pi_{A/B}(ij). \quad (13)$$

Here, the payoff operator is defined by assigning classical payoff values to each computational basis state as $\Pi_A(00) = 3$, $\Pi_A(01) = 0$, $\Pi_A(10) = 5$, $\Pi_A(11) = 1$ for Alice, and $\Pi_B(00) = 3$, $\Pi_B(01) = 5$, $\Pi_B(10) = 0$, $\Pi_B(11) = 1$ for Bob. These coefficients directly correspond to those appearing in Eqs. (5) and (6). This operator-based formulation is completely equivalent to the probabilistic averaging discussed in Sec. 2.1, but the use of the density matrix clarifies the physical interpretation: the expected payoff is nothing but the quantum expectation value of an observable associated with the payoff structure. This unifies the game-theoretic concept of payoff with the quantum mechanical rule of measurement.

Another advantage of employing the density matrix formalism is that it allows us to evaluate quantities beyond the expected payoff. In particular, the von Neumann entropy

$$S(\rho) = -\text{Tr}(\rho \log \rho) \quad (14)$$

quantifies the degree of classical uncertainty remaining after measurement. In the context of quantum games, this entropy provides a measure of the unpredictability in the outcome distribution generated by the players' strategies. Applied to our framework of interactive sound generation, $S(\rho)$ can be interpreted as a quantifier of the diversity and indeterminacy of musical outcomes arising from the interplay of quantum strategies. For example, low entropy corresponds to deterministic or highly predictable outcomes (musical patterns that are rigidly fixed), whereas high entropy corresponds to rich variability (musical improvisations with greater freedom and unpredictability). Thus, the density matrix not only offers a compact way to describe expected payoffs but also opens the possibility to analyze the informational and qualitative structure of emergent musical improvisation in terms of entropy and related measures.

In summary, quantum strategies modify not only the outcome probabilities but also the way these probabilities interfere, leading to measurable deviations from classical payoff expectations. The density matrix formalism highlights that payoffs can be understood as expectation values of operators and further enables entropy-based analysis of outcome diversity, thereby providing new insights into both quantum game theory and its application to improvisational musical creativity.

Figure 2: System architecture. Players select strategies and press keys, which are sent to the Flask server. The server constructs the quantum circuit, performs measurement to obtain an outcome, looks up the payoff values, and applies the corresponding pitch shifts before returning the results to each player.

3 Interactive Quantum Music System Based on Two-Player Quantum Game

We developed a real-time interactive music generation system grounded in the framework of two-player quantum games. The system allows two participants, Player A and Player B, to choose quantum strategies via a web interface and to generate musical notes whose pitches reflect the outcome of a quantum measurement.

3.1 System Architecture

Figure 2 illustrates the overall flow of the system. Each player selects their strategy parameters (θ, ϕ) and presses a key on the virtual piano keyboard. These inputs (strategy and key information) are sent via WebSocket to a Flask server, which executes the corresponding two-qubit quantum circuit given by Eq. (4) to obtain the final state $|\psi_f\rangle$ with the players' strategies U_A, U_B .

When the first key is pressed in a round, a projective measurement in the computational basis is performed on $|\psi_f\rangle$. This measurement collapses the state to one of the four classical outcomes $|00\rangle, |01\rangle, |10\rangle, |11\rangle$. The outcome is then mapped to payoff values (p_A, p_B) according to the Prisoner's Dilemma payoff table: $(3, 3)$, $(0, 5)$, $(5, 0)$, $(1, 1)$. The neutral baseline payoff is set to 3, so the pitch shift for each player is determined as

$$n_A = n_{\text{input}} + (p_A - 3), \quad (15)$$

$$n_B = n_{\text{input}} + (p_B - 3). \quad (16)$$

For example, a payoff of $p_A = 5$ corresponds to a shift of +2 semitones, while $p_B = 1$ corresponds to a shift of

Figure 3: Screenshots of the developed web interface for Player A (top) and Player B (bottom). The interface shows the players' strategies, the round state (collapsed or not), the measurement outcome, and the resulting payoff-based pitch shifts.

–2. These transformed pitches are returned to the clients and played back using Tone.js. The round is considered collapsed until a new round is explicitly triggered, ensuring that the same outcome is consistently used within a round.

3.2 Web-Based Graphical Interface

Figure 3 shows screenshots of the web-based GUI for Player A and Player B. Each player can adjust their strategy parameters (θ, ϕ) via sliders and immediately see the current round status, including whether the quantum state has collapsed, the most recent outcome, and the corresponding payoff shifts. The virtual piano keyboard provides an intuitive way to trigger rounds and generate sound. Once a player presses a key, the measurement-induced collapse occurs and the outcome is fixed until the next round is initiated.

3.3 Expected Musical Outcomes

To analyze the mapping between strategies and resulting pitches, we evaluated the expected output notes as functions of Player A's angle θ_A , for fixed values of Player B's strategy θ_B . Figure 4 shows the expected note values (lines) together with sampled measurement outcomes (markers). At the classical limits $\theta_A = 0$ and $\theta_A = \pi$, the strategies reduce to deterministic choices corresponding to cooperation or defection. In these cases, the expectation values coincide with the sampled outcomes, and no statistical fluctuation is observed. By contrast, for intermediate values of θ_A , the quantum strategies produce superposed states, and measurement leads to probabilistic outcomes. This results in fluctuations of the sampled notes around the smooth expectation-value curves.

Musically, this means that extreme strategic choices yield stable, predictable pitch relations, while intermediate quantum strategies generate audible variability, reflecting the probabilistic nature of quantum measurement and the influence of entanglement. In this way, the figure illustrates how quantum interference reshapes the correlation between players' actions and their resulting sonic outputs.

Figure 4: Expected output notes as a function of Player A's strategy θ_A . Solid and dashed-dotted lines indicate expected pitch values for two choices of Player B's strategy θ_B . Open markers correspond to sampled outcomes from projective measurements in separate rounds.

3.4 Discussion

The proposed system provides a novel framework in which quantum game dynamics are directly translated into musical interactions. By linking payoff values to pitch shifts relative to a neutral baseline, the game-theoretic consequences of quantum measurement become perceivable as sound. The inclusion of round-based collapse ensures that players experience the probabilistic but outcome-fixed nature of quantum measurement within a musical context. This interactive system not only demonstrates the feasibility of integrating quantum-inspired mechanics into musical performance but also offers an accessible platform for exploring quantum decision-making in education, cognition, and the arts.

Here we comment on the possible interpretation of the payoff values. In this system, the payoff values are not interpreted primarily as rewards, but as shared rules that define the structure of interplay between the two players. They constitute common knowledge: both performers understand in advance that a given outcome (e.g., “defection” against “cooperation”) will correspond to a specific pitch shift. Thus, each player's decision is made in anticipation of how the musical context will be reshaped by the opponent's move.

Musically, the baseline payoff of 3 corresponds to the neutral key center (e.g., C4), while other values induce relative transpositions: a payoff of 5 raises the pitch, 0 lowers it more drastically, and 1 produces a smaller downward

shift. These shifts amount to transient key changes that embody the dynamics of negotiation and expectation between the players, rather than simple reward or punishment.

4 Beyond Sound: Music as a Medium for Quantum Meta-Decision

In this work, music functions less as an end than as a medium for exploring how quantum-level choices (made in the space of potentiality) become manifest as outcomes. Quantum strategies do not prescribe fixed actions, but define transformations that shape how states evolve and collapse upon measurement. Such choices are inherently relational, since each outcome arises through interplay with another agent.

In this sense, “choosing a strategy” constitutes a *meta-decision*: a decision not about what occurs, but about how possibilities unfold and interfere with those chosen by others. Music provides a natural ground for this analogy: harmony and dissonance mirror quantum interference, while improvisation exemplifies contextual offers and responsive choices that reshape future trajectories. In particular, jazz interplay illustrates how each phrase both expresses an idea and sets the stage for the partner’s next move, just as quantum strategies redefine outcome probabilities.

Thus, the proposed quantum-game-based musical system offers both a formal and experiential model of entangled decision-making. It demonstrates how sound can enact a theory of relation and emergence, extending beyond computation or aesthetics into a broader inquiry of how the possible becomes actual.

5 Conclusion

We have developed a web-based interactive music system that integrates two-player quantum game theory with real-time sound generation. By mapping the outcomes of quantum strategies and measurements to musical pitch shifts, the system provides an intuitive way for participants to experience quantum interference, probabilistic collapse, and entangled decision-making through sound. Each player’s musical output reflects both their own strategic choice and its relational dependence on the opponent’s choice, thus transforming abstract quantum interactions into perceptible auditory events.

This work demonstrates that music can serve as more than an artistic output: it can function as a medium for exploring quantum meta-decision processes, where choices are not direct actions but structural configurations of possible outcomes. In this sense, the system resonates with improvisatory practices such as jazz performance, in which each phrase offers a context that shapes the partner’s response and redirects the course of the interaction.

Beyond music and performance, the framework has broader implications for education and human-computer interaction, offering an accessible platform for

engaging with quantum concepts in a tangible way. Future extensions could involve multi-player games, adaptive strategy learning, or even hybrid integration with real quantum hardware. Ultimately, this research illustrates how sound can embody the logic of quantum games, opening new directions for both creative practice and the study of entangled decision-making.

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